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TOWARDS DEEP STRATEGIC THEORY

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This dissertation is the sole work of the author, and has not been accepted in any previous application for a degree; all quotations and sources of information have been acknowledged.

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of a stylized 'G' followed by a horizontal line that extends to the right and then curves downwards.

Signed: **Guillaume Chapron**

Date: **19/03/2023**

Abstract

The return of war in Europe and more generally of great power competition on the global stage illustrates that strategy remains a difficult endeavour. While weapons and armies have radically changed with technological progress during the past centuries, strategy seems to have escaped this progress as if there was something in its core nature that would make it immune to human mastery. A new technological revolution, the artificial intelligence (AI) revolution, is however now massively disrupting many human activities that were previously beyond reach of computers. A natural question is whether strategy will soon follow and be performed by AI to give rise to what I call deep strategies. This dissertation explores this question under the light of the most recent advances in AI and adopts a forward-looking perspective regarding the possibilities, challenges and implications for the future of strategy. Specifically, this dissertation starts by re-stating sometimes forgotten important traits of strategy that make it so difficult to practice. It then proceeds by explaining how strategic thinking requires modelling and is somewhat reflected in the mathematics behind a new algorithm in AI, deep reinforcement learning. It describes what AI has been able to achieve with known strategic games, ranging from board games such as Go to more realistic games of tactics or diplomacy requiring negotiation, persuasion and betrayal skills. It presents which forms a deep strategic theory could take by revisiting Clausewitz's *On War* through complexity theory and developing wargames focused on levers. It discusses the challenges such deep strategic theory will face, especially given the fundamentally psychological nature of strategy and that strategic actions always ripple through unintended system effects. It concludes by reflecting on the broader implications of AI or deep strategies for the practice of strategy.

289 words

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INTRODUCTION

Strategy: use and abuse of a word

The word ‘strategy’ is today ubiquitous. Counting the number of times one encounters the word in a single day reveals a pattern where every organisation, from the local gardening club to a regional government agency or a multinational corporation, has its own strategy that is prominently highlighted when conducting its operations or communicating to the broader public. A word frequency analysis in the whole text corpus of Google Books shows that the occurrence of the word ‘strategy’ has dramatically increased since WWII.¹ There is virtually no topic or issue that does not have or less need its own strategy and the modern world seems to now have become a ground where strategies are constantly being elaborated, implemented and revised. Most of these occurrences of the word strategy however refer to non-military issues and depart from its original meaning.

The word strategy is quite old and first appeared in ancient Greek as στρατηγία, stratēgía, meaning the art of the general, itself from στρατηγός, stratēgós, for the general of an army, deriving from στρατός (stratós, an army) and ἄγω (ágō, the act of commanding). The Romans kept the term strategus and used it to refer to the commander of an army. The Byzantines had strategos similarly for the one who commands an army.² But after the collapse of the Roman and Byzantine empires, the word strategy largely disappeared for several centuries in Western Europe. It reappeared in 18th century, in French and then English military writings before being widely adopted by military schools, under the inspiration of the Prussian military.³

The contemporary omnipresence of strategy does therefore not reflect a historical prevalence of the term. During most of Western civilisation history, the word was largely unused and when it was in the ancient times or after the French Revolution, its meaning was much narrower than now. Neither does this ubiquity reveal a proficiency in strategic thinking.⁴

¹ https://books.google.com/ngrams/graph?content=strategy&year_start=1800&year_end=2019&corpus=en-US-2019&smoothing=0 Interestingly, changing the corpus from US to British English reveals a decline from 2006 to 2010, now stabilised.

² (Coutau-Bégarie 2011)

³ Ibid.

⁴ Note the opposite: an absence of the word ‘strategy’ does not mean that thinking corresponding to the original meaning of the word is also absent. Ancient China did not have a word for strategy. Still, it had an elaborated thinking of strategy, having produced one of the oldest treaty on the matter in the form of *The Art of War* (Sun

Organisations that have strategies do not appear to be immune to failure, and the natural experts in strategic practice, military organisations, do not enjoy higher success rates in their actions. Strategy does not seem to be mastered and practiced everywhere well. As Lawrence Freedman writes “the world of strategy is full of disappointment and frustration, of means not working and ends not reached”.⁵

A timely illustration is the ongoing war of Russia against Ukraine whereby, after now one year, everything and its contrary has more or less been said. It is remarkable that few could figure out whether Russia would attack. Many intelligence agencies and scholars projected their own rationality on Putin and failed to understand his different own rationality.⁶ Understanding strategic interactions is difficult in the moment and becomes explainable only retrospectively. The problem is that it is in the moment that strategic decisions have to be made. The war in Ukraine has restarted history, at least in Western Europe, and put us in a strategic moment that illustrates again strategy remains a formidable challenge. While our technologies have massively changed since Clausewitz, it seems our ability to do strategy has largely remained the same, at best.

The chimpanzees of the future

In that context, it is important to reflect on the technological revolutions that have happened since Clausewitz published its opus *On War*. Clausewitz witnessed the first industrial revolution (1780–1840), which was to be followed by the second one (1870–1920), the scientific revolution (1980–1970) and now the digital revolution (1975–2020). All have profoundly changed the world, including the conduct of wars. However, they have not solved the difficulty of strategy. Nevertheless, a new technological revolution seems to be on the verge of happening with recent advances in machine learning. Let us call this revolution the artificial intelligence (AI) revolution.

There have been exponential achievements in AI and what was thought to have been impossible or years away a few months ago is now integrated into mainstream products, thanks to new algorithms such as transformers or deep reinforcement learning. The most

Tzu 2008).

⁵ (Freedman 2013)

⁶ (Banco et al. 2023)

striking illustration for a non-technical audience may be ChatGPT-like programs that easily generate texts, pictures, music, novels, and short videos. While the slogan “the future is now” has been repeated ad nauseam to market innovations, there are troubling signals that indeed the future may actually be now with a science-fiction novel magazine having closed submissions after a surge of AI-generated submissions.⁷ The AI revolution has also naturally been widely discussed in defence and military circles.⁸ Most of the focus has been on the importance of big data analytics, autonomous weapons or how artificial intelligence has become a new global race for geopolitical power. Surprising and worrying uses of AI for potential military purposes have also been found with e.g. deep learning algorithms used to design better drugs being also suitable to design more lethal chemical weapons.⁹ These achievements are for the moment technical but one general question is lurking: if AI can now generate most of human creation, could it also generate strategic thoughts?

Reviewing an acclaimed book on AI in conflicts, Lawrence Freedman argued that “if AI receives a lot of data and a narrow goal, it will be tactically brilliant in ways that human commanders could never match—but AI will never be a true strategist”.¹⁰ Does this close the discussion? One would be very well careful with issuing a final verdict on emerging technologies, perhaps even more when being a qualified expert on the matter. After all, Robert Metcalfe, who invented the Ethernet networking protocol, declared in 1995 that “almost all of the many predictions now being made about 1996 hinge on the Internet’s continuing exponential growth. But I predict the Internet will soon go spectacularly supernova and in 1996 catastrophically collapse”.¹¹ The future role of AI in strategy is therefore particularly interesting. On the one hand, we could agree that strategy is at the core of what makes us humans. On the other hand, we could also claim that what matters is not *Homo sapiens* but having adequate cognitive abilities. Indeed, chimpanzees do practice strategy, albeit to a more limited extent, and with the most recent AI now performing better than the majority of students in standard exams¹², the question arises whether humans will become chimpanzees of the future, outsmarted by machines, even in strategic thinking.

⁷ (Edwards 2023)

⁸ (Brose 2022; Kanaan 2020; Scharre 2019; Tangredi and Galdorisi 2021)

⁹ (Urbina et al. 2022)

¹⁰ (Freedman 2021)

¹¹ https://www.elon.edu/u/imagining/expert_predictions/from-the-ether-predicting-the-internets-catastrophic-collapse-and-ghost-sites-galore-in-1996/

¹² I am referring here to ChatGPT-4 released just a few days before submitting this dissertation. See <https://openai.com/research/gpt-4> documenting its performance on simulated exams.

Structure of the argument

This dissertation does not aim to come with a definitive answer but instead to explore this question under the light of the most recent advances in AI and to adopt a forward-looking perspective regarding challenges and implications for the future of strategy. Specifically, this dissertation starts by re-stating sometimes forgotten important traits of strategy that make it so difficult to practice. It then proceeds by explaining how strategic thinking is somewhat reflected in the mathematics behind AI, presents what AI has been able to achieve in strategic games before discussing which form a deep strategic theory could take. It concludes by reflecting on the broader implications of strategic AI. It draws from a variety of sources, ranging from historical and contemporary strategy thinking, complex systems theory and naturally AI, although I have kept only the most necessary technical details and have focused on how these details relate to strategic thinking.

THE STATE OF STRATEGIC THEORY

What is strategy?

A first and necessary step when discussing strategy is obviously to define strategy. Because strategy is ubiquitous, it is important to make sure that the term is clearly and consistently defined. The definition this dissertation retains derives from the one proposed by French military scholar Beaufre: “the art of the dialectic of wills using force to resolve their conflicts”.¹³ It can be broadened by the reflection of another French military scholar, Coutau-Bégarie, that strategy is “a matter of intelligence driven by will”¹⁴ which is somewhat echoed by Freedman’s concise and elegant definition: “the art of crafting power”.¹⁵ French general Desportes explains that strategy occurs when “two actors pursue divergent interests in a shared space”.¹⁶ It is important to stress that these definitions of strategy do not include what is usually understood as corporate strategy and about which an abundant literature has been

¹³ (Beaufre 2012)

¹⁴ (Motte 2021)

¹⁵ (Freedman 2013)

¹⁶ (Desportes 2019)

produced (this includes as well any so-called strategy for a university, a government agency, etc, which is simply a plan to reach future goals). Coutau-Bégarie explained that “a corporation secretes its own purpose, which is profit, whereas strategy is dependent on an external purpose”.¹⁷ Still, although I do not consider that business strategy meets the criteria to qualify as strategy, I adopt a definition of strategy that is wider than pure military. Such a choice is not new and can be found in the oldest writing on the matter, with Sun Tzu’s well-known maxim telling that “to subdue the enemy without fighting is the acme of skill”.¹⁸ This view is also not outdated or reserved to ancient times, as British strategist Liddell Hart appears to echo Sun Tzu when arguing for an indirect approach in strategy: “the longest way round is often the shortest way home”.¹⁹ While strategy is about confrontation, it does not necessary imply kinetic confrontation through the use of military force (or threat thereof) and increasingly includes diverse dimensions such as geoeconomics.²⁰

The epistemological challenges of strategy

Despite the earliest mentions of strategic thinking dating back to the 5th century BC and mentions of strategy being today ubiquitous, a unifying theory of strategy appears to be lacking. Ideally, such a strategy would be based on a few, narrowly defined, first principles that would remain valid and shed lights on all kinds of strategic interactions. There have been many attempts at enumerating and documenting invariants that reoccur in strategy. But the traits of these invariants and how they can be articulated to form a coherent strategic whole guiding real-world strategic choices is lacking. For his theory of strategy, Colin Gray listed more than a dozen key components, which include political, economic, geographical, historical, technological, etc, components.²¹ The problem however with a long list where everything is important is that it precludes identifying what the most important is. As the abstract expressionist German painter Hans Hofmann once said “the ability to simplify means to eliminate the unnecessary so that the necessary may speak”. It appears scholars have struggled in letting the necessary speak in strategy, a consequence of which being that a theory of strategy that would function like a scientific theory remains missing.

¹⁷ (Coutau-Bégarie 2011)

¹⁸ (Sun Tzu 2008)

¹⁹ (Hart 1929)

²⁰ (Blackwill and Harris 2016; Kittrie 2016; Demarais 2022)

²¹ (Gray 2018)

Aiming to establish a scientific theory of strategy may be putting the bar quite high but it is nevertheless interesting to reflect on which criteria such theory would need to satisfy.²² First, the theory would need to display what is called internal consistency. This means that it would not generate propositions that contradict each other. Second, there would need to be correspondence or alignment between the theoretical propositions by the theory and the observable facts that it pretends to explain. Third, the theory would need to offer a coherent set of predictions that would serve as a basis to test and validate the theory. Fourth, the theory would need to remain parsimonious in the sense that it would not rely on unnecessary complex or ad-hoc conditions to remain valid when confronted to new evidence. Finally, the theory would need to be falsifiable, which means it would be possible to prove the theory wrong and reject it. This criterion is fundamentally important to make the difference between a theory, a system of beliefs or an ideology.

Strategic theory is today not able to meet these criteria, echoing Clausewitz introductory note that “it is a very difficult task to construct a scientific theory for the art of war”.²³ The source of this difficulty may be found in the traits of strategy itself that make it less amenable to the standard scientific method. I call these traits the predicaments of the strategist and I believe that for AI to be able to master strategy, it will need to escape these predicaments better than humans.

The five predicaments of the strategist

There are several traits making strategy harder to be explained by a scientific theory than other natural or social phenomena. I outline below what I believe are the five most salient ones.

1) Strategy is an adversarial dialectic: it is as much shaped by the strategist than by an adversary. Clausewitz explained that “I am not my own master, for my adversary dictates his law to me as I dictate mine to him”²⁴, echoed by Mao Zedong arguing that “our will very quickly meets the independent will of the adversary, which makes the course of action depend as much on his intentions as on ours”.²⁵ Desportes summarises that the strategist “is

²² (Vorms 2011)

²³ (Clausewitz 2007)

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ (Tse-Tung 2015)

the subject, but the adversary who is his object is himself a subject of which the strategist is the object”.²⁶ A lesson of which according to Napoléon Bonaparte being that “the art of war consists of being always able ... to do what your enemy does not expect”.²⁷

2) Strategy can neither be planned nor repeated: a consequence of this adversarial dialectical nature is, as Helmuth von Moltke (the Elder) asserted, that “no plan survives first contact with the enemy”.²⁸ More generally, Sun Tzu observed that “a general does not seek to repeat his exploits, but endeavors to respond to the infinite variety of circumstances”.²⁹ Helmuth von Moltke again elaborated further: “never can the means employed or the rules established yesterday by the greatest strategists be applied twice”.³⁰ The crux of the matter is that if a strategy works today, it will not work tomorrow and for the reason that it works today.

3) Strategy makes causality recursive: “cause and effect determine each other; the strategic actor is driven by the system that is itself his product”.³¹ It is only possible to determine the cause-and-effect relationship between two events after they have occurred. One can say that event A caused event B, but one could not have said that event A would certainly cause event B. Causality in strategy can also be paradoxical, where preparing for war can bring peace, while pursuing peace can invite war.³² It is also not possible to learn from repeated ‘experiments’ because “the personality of the experimenter has a direct influence on the results of the experiment”.³³

4) Strategy is less about numbers than about minds: Ferdinand Foch understood that “the most powerful weapon on earth is the human soul on fire”.³⁴ Echoing Foch about the battle of the Marne (1914), Helmuth von Moltke, chief of staff of the German army, admitted “that men who have retreated for more than a fortnight, lying on the ground and half-dead with fatigue, can take up their rifles again and attack at the sound of a bugle, is something which we did not learn in military schools”.³⁵ An excellent strategist is therefore one who is able to achieve victory despite having technological or numerical inferiority.

5) Strategy cannot be true: if strategy is about breaking rules, there cannot be rules in strategy. French general Desportes elaborates at length on this fundamental point: “if there

²⁶ (Desportes 2019)

²⁷ (Colson 2015)

²⁸ (Hughes 2009)

²⁹ (Sun Tzu 2008)

³⁰ (Hughes 2009)

³¹ (Desportes 2019)

³² (Luttwak 2002)

³³ (Desportes 2019)

³⁴ (Autin 1998)

³⁵ Ibid.

were one true strategy, there would be no need for strategy: strategic truth would kill the very idea of strategy”.³⁶ Strategy “admits as a postulate the absence of truth and the inability to master the fundamental laws that govern the strategic space”.³⁷ He even goes further by arguing that “the very fact of having imagined a type of action means that it will not come to succeed because the adversary will have prepared accordingly”.³⁸

To summarise, strategy is as much shaped by the one who does it than by the one it is aimed at, cannot be planned or learnt, blurs cause and effect in a non-repeatable fashion, cannot be summarised by arithmetic ratios of strengths and like some sort of reverse philosopher’s stone, turns any truth into untruth. I am not aware of any other natural or social phenomenon that displays the same level of conceptual difficulties. Does this mean that strategists are condemned to forever struggle with apprehending a phenomenon that knows no truth? Or can recent advances in science, especially in AI, open the door of truth to strategy? Regardless of the answer, it is important to recognise that strategy is akin to science because it involves a form of modelling. Since this is a blunt statement, it requires some explanations.

THE DAWN OF STRATEGIC AI

Strategy is modelling

The term model may elicit scepticism as it may be associated with a scientist worldview according to which the world can be reduced to equations. Similar critics are found in Clausewitz against “unreasonable theories” used by “limited and ignorant minds to justify their congenital incompetence”.³⁹ Scepticism against models stems however generally from a misunderstanding of what models are. Models are simply abstract representations of the world and can be of verbal, visual, qualitative or quantitative forms among others. The painter Picasso and statistician Cox were to some extent both modellers and “made such similar statements about the central importance of abstraction to insight”⁴⁰.

³⁶ (Desportes 2019)

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ (Clausewitz 2007)

⁴⁰ (Hobbs and Hooten 2015)

It turns out that creating abstract representations is something that humans permanently do when interacting with their environment. Being human is being a modeller. Similarly, being a strategist is being a modeller too, albeit a kind of modeller that is confronted to a situation governed by the above-described predicaments and therefore much more difficult to apprehend. Every strategist builds his or her own abstract representation or mental model of the adversarial interaction faced. There needs to be an abstract representation of the consequences of one's actions, especially of how the adversary is going to react. Telling that strategy cannot be understood by models is wrong because strategy is modelling. Without a model, strategy is random. Strategy has historically been mostly done with verbal or mental models.

Critics of the use of models in strategy ignore that what models can be blamed for also applies to human strategists. Formal models – mathematical representations of complex phenomena with a well-defined syntax – are often discarded because they do not include many factors that one can legitimately deem essential to understand a phenomenon. But very often, a verbal abstract representation of the same phenomenon will omit many factors too, albeit less visibly. The strength of models, especially formal ones, is that they make explicit the omission of such key factors while an expert opinion or what Clausewitz called a strategic genius does not and is therefore more immune to critics. Models are the best antidote to the fallacy of appeal to authority.

Formal models, when coupled with computations, have often provided new insights into complex phenomena that exceeded what humans could naturally apprehend. However, strategy has so far hardly benefited from progress in computing. The question is therefore whether today's advances in computational modelling may provide a better or at least alternative way of doing strategy. To answer this question, it is necessary to narrow down strategy to its most fundamental nature.

The mathematics of strategy

In US military thinking, strategy is often formalised as Lykke's three-legged stool model consisting of ends (objectives), ways (courses of action) and means (instruments)⁴¹. This

⁴¹ (Lykke 1989)

definition has been described as being “to modern strategists [what] Einstein’s equation $E=mc^2$ is to physicists”⁴² and it is interesting that it is not that dissimilar from a mathematical object central to decision theory and known as a Markov Decision Process (MDP). A MDP is defined by a tuple (S, A, R, P, γ) where S are all the possible states of the system, A are all the possible actions that one can take, R are rewards that are associated by having the system reaching a specific state, taking a specific action or both, P represents the probability of transition between a state to another after an action is taken, and γ is the discount rate, indicating how much the far future is valued compared to the immediate future. Solving a MDP aims at finding the optimal sequence (similar to ways in Lykke’s model) of actions (similar to means) to take at each state of the system to maximise rewards (in practice similar to ends). By assigning a high reward to a specific end state, practicing strategy becomes equal to solving a MDP.

Such an approach to strategy would certainly have appealed to Jomini and be mocked by Clausewitz, had MDP existed in their times. It is obviously impossible to list all possible states in which adversaries could find themselves and all possible actions they could exert against each other, as well as to know exactly how adversaries would move from states to states following actions taken. Therefore, while strategy can be cast as a mathematical problem, it can in practice not be solved mathematically. However, it is important to refer to the point made above about strategy being an exercise in modelling. Confronted to the enormous complexity of the real world, master strategists excel at extracting the most relevant information to enormously simplify the world into a mental representation they can apprehend. It turns out that approximating the world is also the foundation of recent advances in AI.

Without entering into technical details, these advances fall under the AI branch of deep reinforcement learning (DRL).⁴³ DRL is a subfield of reinforcement learning ⁴⁴ itself derived from the study of MDP, and is one of the most vibrant fields of AI research today, with ground-breaking discoveries happening almost every week. DRL brings together reinforcement learning and deep learning. Reinforcement learning is a way of learning by trial and error, where an agent tries different actions and gets feedback (rewards or penalties)

⁴² (Echevarria 2013)

⁴³ (Dong, Ding, and Zhang 2020; Graesser and Keng 2019; Lapan 2020; Plaat 2022; Sanghi 2021; Sewak 2019)

⁴⁴ (Sutton and Barto 2018)

from the environment. Deep learning is a way of using neural networks to learn complex patterns from data. It is thanks to DRL that machines have been able to master strategic games. Strategic games are understood as being games, often zero-sum but not always, where players with their specific interests take actions with the aim to maximise their goals. They are different from game theory. I term “deep strategies” the use of DRL in strategic games and “deep strategic theory” the knowledge that can be learnt from DRL-inspired strategies. I now turn to specific games that have been milestones in the dawn of deep strategies.

An algorithm to rule them all

In the beginning was Move 37 in Seoul

The beginning of the era of deep strategies can be dated to 2016 when the London based start-up company DeepMind published in *Nature* its AI program, AlphaGo, to play Go.⁴⁵ Go had for a long time been considered a grand challenge for AI. The game has very high number of moves which makes it difficult for traditional AI methods. In addition, while the rules of Go are simple, the strategies and patterns are more subtle and diverse than chess. One needs creativity and intuition, which are difficult to emulate with conventional algorithms. The game also lacks a clear evaluation function, which makes it hard to determine who is winning or losing at any given moment. To overcome these obstacles, AlphaGo was trained on 30 million moves from human games and then improved by self-play. AlphaGo made history in March 2016 by defeating four to one Lee Sedol, one of the world’s top Go players, in Seoul, South Korea.⁴⁶ Move 37 during the second game by AlphaGo was highly unconventional and generated widespread incredulity among the Go community, but settled victory for AlphaGo.⁴⁷ After the games, Lee Sedol explained “I thought AlphaGo was based on probability calculation and that it was merely a machine. But when I saw this move, I changed my mind. Surely, AlphaGo is creative”. One year later, DeepMind published also in *Nature* an improved version, AlphaGo Zero, which learnt to play Go entirely from scratch, starting from random moves and improving by playing against itself.⁴⁸ It discovered new strategies and tactics that were not influenced by human knowledge or biases and defeated

⁴⁵ (Silver et al. 2016)

⁴⁶ See the non-technical but highly informative documentary “AlphaGo - The Movie” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WXuK6gekUIY>

⁴⁷ (Metz 2016)

⁴⁸ (Silver et al. 2017)

AlphaGo by 100 games to 0. In 2018, DeepMind released AlphaZero⁴⁹, a generalised version of AlphaGo Zero that can play other games than Go such as chess and shogi, followed in 2020 by MuZero that can master games without knowing their rules.⁵⁰

Tactics with AlphaStar

The online video game StarCraft II was the next challenge set for AI. Playing StarCraft II requires anticipation, resource management, scouting, deception, and adaptation to execute complex combat manoeuvres. There are hundreds of soldiers in the multiple race (Terran, Protoss, and Zerg) armies that can take 10^{26} actions at any step.⁵¹ In addition, the game has a partially observable state, meaning a player cannot see the whole map and has to infer the opponent actions and intentions. In 2019, DeepMind published in *Nature* its program AlphaStar that was able to achieve Grandmaster level at the game, which meant it belonged to the top 0.15% of players (noteworthy and unlike Go, this AI was not able to beat the best human players).⁵² One of the DeepMind engineers explained that the strategic relevance of AlphaStar was that the game lacks the “availability of a dynamics model whose predictions are accurate (and cheap) enough to be used for planning, and the availability of perfect state information”.⁵³

Total fog of war with DeepNash

Efforts in strategic AI then moved to the game of Stratego which brings a very difficult challenge to human strategists and machines alike as it features an extreme version of Clausewitz’s fog of war. Each of the two players has 40 pieces placed on a board, but a player cannot see where the pieces of its opponent are. The goal of the game is to capture the opponent’s flag or as many pieces as possible. Stratego has long been considered a grand challenge for AI. The space of possibilities of the game is 10^{535} and dwarfs the previous games tackled by AI such as Go. While poker is also an imperfect-information game, Stratego has 10^{66} unobservable possibilities at the beginning of the game. In December 2022, DeepMind reported in *Science* about their new AI, DeepNash, that learnt to play Stratego.⁵⁴ The lead author explained that “the sheer complexity of the number of possible outcomes in

⁴⁹ (Silver et al. 2018)

⁵⁰ (Schrittwieser et al. 2020)

⁵¹ (Garisto 2019)

⁵² (Vinyals et al. 2019)

⁵³ (Risi and Preuss 2020)

⁵⁴ (Perolat et al. 2022)

Stratego means algorithms that perform well on perfect-information games, and even those that work for poker, don't work".⁵⁵ DeepMind's algorithm however can "handle huge amounts of uncertainty in the form of imperfect information, more than has previously been possible".⁵⁶ Trained by self-play during billions of games, it does not aim to optimise itself by exploring through the game tree but by trying to find the best strategy that works against any possible opponent (hence the name DeepNash, in reference to the Nash equilibrium, a strategy where neither players can improve their outcomes by changing their strategies).

Geopolitics with Cicero

While all these achievements came from DeepMind the last but certainly not least remarkable one comes from the research branch of Meta AI.⁵⁷ The team at Meta AI set its goal on the game of Diplomacy, a strategy game taking place among European countries before WWI and that requires negotiating with multiple players.⁵⁸ The objective of the game is to control as many supply centres as possible. It is worth looking in details at Diplomacy's rulebook to understand that what Meta AI has achieved may be more significant than AlphaGo defeating Lee Sedol in 2016. Specifically, what are called "spring turns" in the game start with a "diplomatic phase" where the seven players can meet, converse, bargain, spy on each other, communicate "information, denouncements, threats, spreading of rumors", with none of what being said or agreed upon being binding to them.⁵⁹ One magazine explains that "the level of scheming, backstabbing, false promises and general Machiavellian antics that people get up to in the game are such that it is banned from many friendly gaming groups".⁶⁰ The game does not include tactical combat dimensions as it is more a diplomatic simulation game. In December 2022, Meta AI published in *Science* their model, Cicero, an AI program to play Diplomacy. It uniquely merges a dialogue module and a strategic reasoning module and is trained from human games with additional self-play. Cicero performed twice as good as the average human players in an online Diplomacy league and was ranked in the top 10% of all participating players.⁶¹

⁵⁵ (Ananthaswamy 2022)

⁵⁶ (Snyder 2022)

⁵⁷ One could also mention the AI OpenAI Five defeating the world champions at the Dota 2 game.

⁵⁸ (Hutson 2022)

⁵⁹ (The Avalon Hill Game Co 2000)

⁶⁰ (Coldewey 2022)

⁶¹ (META FUNDAMENTAL AI RESEARCH DIPLOMACY TEAM (FAIR) et al. 2022)

Military applications

These advances in AI are impressive and one follow-up question is immediately whether they have been noticed and used by the military. Here it is important to note this means AI being used to make complex tactical or strategic decisions and not to optimise logistics or the targeting of missiles. Interestingly, the publication of AlphaStar had been criticised by emeritus professor in robotics Noel Sharkey who warned that “military analysts will certainly be eyeing the successful AlphaStar real-time strategies as a clear example of the advantages of AI for battlefield planning”,⁶² to which David Silver from DeepMind replied that “to say that this has any kind of military use is saying no more than to say an AI for chess could be used to lead to military applications”.⁶³ It turns out however that the critic was more correct than the author, as several military research institutes have now built on this research. A study commissioned by the UK Ministry of Defence reviewed how AI could be applied to wargames and concluded that “wargames are in many cases not fundamentally harder than playing StarCraft” and highlighted the need to develop a flexible approach so that e.g. it would not be required to retrain the model once a new weapon is introduced.⁶⁴ Other work recommended “a research agenda that sees modelling, simulation, gaming, and analysis as related and intertwined”.⁶⁵

The German Bundeswehr has built on DeepMind’s AlphaStar to develop a DRL algorithm (“ReLeGSim”) for tactical decision-making on the battlefield.⁶⁶ The algorithm is designed to be an AI assistant to battalion commanders. While the study is experimental, it reports very interesting results that deserve to be quoted in full: “[ReLeGSim] employs tank companies mainly in open terrain. It uses long-range weapon systems at an early stage to influence the balance of power in its favour. In addition, it tasks remote JISR units to ensure early detection and engagement of enemy forces. For movements of friendly forces, the RL agent exploits terrain outside the effective ranges of enemy weapon systems. Since no such information had been given, the agent must have 'learned' the ranges of the enemy’s individual weapon systems. In another scenario, the RL agent purposefully slowed down follow-on forces by employing minefields, thus preventing them from closing up to advance elements.”

⁶² (*The Guardian* 2019)

⁶³ (*BBC News* 2019)

⁶⁴ (Goodman, Risi, and Lucas 2020)

⁶⁵ (Davis and Bracken 2022)

⁶⁶ (Doll et al. 2021)

Some other research has focused on playing simple wargames with AI. In a simple study, AlphaZero has been modified to play the wargame Coral Sea, an hexagonal type of naval warfare board game.⁶⁷ Coral Sea differs from other board games because several pieces can occupy the same place, the landscape is asymmetric (one player may start at a disadvantage and therefore learning the optimal strategy becomes a lot more difficult), and has a lower strategic depth.⁶⁸ With fine-tuned modifications of AlphaZero it was possible for the AI to exceed the performance of average players. The Swedish Defence Research Agency has produced several reports on using deep reinforcement learning in strategy⁶⁹ and concluded that AlphaZero could play the game of Risk (a strategy and diplomacy board game) and reached an expert human level, although challenges remained such as the availability of computing power.⁷⁰ It is too early to have military applications of DeepNash and Cicero as the papers were published late 2022, but similarly to AlphaZero and AlphaStar, one can certainly expect that military research agencies will investigate possible applications.

A FORMALISATION OF STRATEGIC INTERACTIONS

AI does not play with chameleons

One could legitimately argue that, while such human-level proficiency achieved by AI is genuinely impressive, it does not and cannot apply to strategic interactions in the real world. The reason is that although the above-mentioned games are challenging for both humans and computers alike, they remain bounded by what the creators of the games have decided. Go has only a limited set of elegant rules. StarCraft II adds complexity but does not allow, for example, temporary alliances between two of the three races. Stratego includes an unambiguous version of Clausewitz's fog of war and completely ignores friction. Finally, while Diplomacy brings some of the complexity of the human mind, it remains a gross simplification of politics during both peace and war times. By contrast, the real world cannot easily be described by a set of simple, immutable, almost mathematical rules, from which it

⁶⁷ (Moy and Shekh 2019)

⁶⁸ (Lantz et al. 2017)

⁶⁹ (Bethdavid 2020; Blomqvist 2020)

⁷⁰ (Cohen et al. 2020)

would be possible to make reliable predictions about future affairs. War is “a true chameleon” said Clausewitz⁷¹ and if war constantly changes, it is unclear how we could build a model of it that would help strategists make better decisions.

Clausewitzian complexity

It turns out that a possible answer to this conundrum may be found by re-reading *On War* but with a complexity theory lens. Complexity can be best understood by referring back to its etymology⁷²: plexus in Latin means braided or entwined and adding the prefix con- (with) refers to an “intricate intertwining or interconnectivity of elements within a system, and between a system and its environment”.⁷³ The theory of complex systems stems from the observation that some systems are more than the sum of their parts.⁷⁴ Parts in a system interact with each other to create emergent aggregate behaviours that cannot be understood by adopting a reductionist lens focusing on individual parts. Complex systems are often characterised by non-linear dynamics, feedback loops or tipping points and attractors.⁷⁵ There are many complex systems – most systems are actually complex – such as the Earth climate, ecosystems and organisms, the human brain, human societies, political institutions, or markets. Some complex systems are called adaptive in the sense that the parts or rather agents forming these systems react to or anticipate what other agents are doing and adapt to changes in their environment.⁷⁶ A cloud is a complex system while a market is a complex adaptive system. Viewing war as a complex system brings important conceptual understanding and epistemological possibilities.⁷⁷

Although not forming a mainstream school of thought in war studies, several scholars have argued that Clausewitz understood war as a complex system ahead of his time since it would be 150 years before complexity theory would emerge as scientific discipline.⁷⁸ *On War* does not define the key principles of complexity theory but Clausewitz seemed to write as if he had their intuitive knowledge. In 1992, Beyerchen was the first scholar to argue that

⁷¹ (Clausewitz 2007)

⁷² (Gell-Mann 1995)

⁷³ (Moffat 2003)

⁷⁴ (Turner, Klimek, and Hanel 2018)

⁷⁵ Ibid.

⁷⁶ (Miller and Page 2007)

⁷⁷ (Cole 2020)

⁷⁸ (Ladyman and Wiesner 2020)

Clausewitz understood war is fundamentally a non-linear phenomenon and therefore cannot be studied by methods that aim to provide “exact analytical solutions”.⁷⁹ He explained that such methods are suitable only to systems that meet two conditions: proportionality (increased input leads to increased outputs in the same proportion) and additivity (a system is strictly equal to the sum of its parts).⁸⁰ Systems are non-linear when they do not obey any of these two conditions and the forethoughtfulness of Clausewitz, Beyerchen argued, was to identify war as such a non-linear system. This is in contrast to Bülow or Jomini who remained locked into linear thinking, with the consequence that “reality has been selectively addressed in order to manipulate it with the tools available”.⁸¹ Linear predictions are problematic in war because it is not possible to calculate the outcomes of an interaction between adversaries, as “war is not an exercise of the will directed at inanimate matter ... In war, the will is directed at an animate object that reacts”.⁸² Clausewitz clarified that “here we are not concerned with the problem of calculating such reactions – that is really part of the already mentioned problem of calculating psychological forces – but rather with the fact that the very nature of interaction is bound to make it unpredictable”.⁸³ Therefore, even if we could obtain accurate measurements of psychological forces, their confrontations would not be measurable. Instead, “a vast array of factors has to be appreciated mostly in light of probabilities alone”.⁸⁴

Several years later, Cole developed further an interpretation of Clausewitz through complexity theory and claimed that Clausewitz’s concept of the paradoxical trinity was a way of understanding the nature of war as a complex adaptive system.⁸⁵ Indeed, Clausewitz appears in many sections to describe many core principles of complexity theory: “we must begin by looking at the nature of the whole; for here more than elsewhere the part and the whole must always be thought of together” or “in war, as in life generally, all parts of the whole are interconnected and thus the effects produced, however small their cause, must influence all subsequent military operations and modify their final outcome to some degree, however slight”⁸⁶. More recently, Friedman made a similar point with a striking illustration:

⁷⁹ (Beyerchen 1992)

⁸⁰ (Beyerchen 2007)

⁸¹ (Beyerchen 1992)

⁸² (Clausewitz 2007)

⁸³ Ibid.

⁸⁴ Ibid.

⁸⁵ (Cole 2020)

⁸⁶ (Clausewitz 2007)

“the butterfly effect is, of course, present in war as well ... A single Serbian terrorist in Sarajevo in 1914 can ignite the world over lunch”.⁸⁷ Reading *On War* with a complexity theory lens may elucidate why Clausewitz has both fascinated and confused generations of scholars and soldiers: “interconnectedness and context, interaction, chance, complexity, indistinct boundaries, feedback effects and so on, all leading to analytical unpredictability – it is no wonder that *On War* has confused and disappointed those looking for a theory of war modeled on the success of Newtonian mechanics”.⁸⁸

Complex war studies as a way forward

Friedman went further by introducing the concept of complex war studies arguing that “current debates about attrition versus maneuver-based approaches, the operational level of war, and so-called grayzone operations all can be informed better by an understanding of Clausewitz’s theories viewed through the lens of complexity”.⁸⁹ If war is a complex system, there is no reason why it cannot be modelled as such. As the head of the New England Complex Systems Institute explains “it is reasonable to postulate that warfare can be better executed by those who understand complex systems than those who focus on simple linear, transparent, classically logical, Newtonian constructs”.⁹⁰ It is important however to not interpret attempts at understanding war through complex system modelling as some sort of Revolution in Military Affairs with the word complexity added. Referring to this latter risk, Bousquet explained that such a “view of warfare is in complete contradiction with the principles of chaos and complexity theory. Warfare cannot be completely predicted or controlled, knowledge is imperfect, and redundancy allows for great adaptability and resilience in the face of contingency”.⁹¹ The next question then becomes how can complex war studies help us develop better models of strategic interactions that may be latter played by AI?

⁸⁷ (Friedman 2022)

⁸⁸ (Beyerchen 1992)

⁸⁹ (Friedman 2022)

⁹⁰ (Bar-Yam 2003)

⁹¹ (Bousquet 2009)

WARGAMING STRATEGY WITH AI

Centre of gravity and levers

It turns out that Clausewitz can again help us. A fundamental concept in *On War*, perhaps the most important, is the centre of gravity (CoG). Endless discussions have taken place about what CoG is, without coming to an agreement. In a reinterpretation of the CoG, Echevarria argued that it “is a “focal point,” neither a strength (or even a source of one) nor a weakness, per se”.⁹² Instead, he explained “CoGs are found only where sufficient connectivity exists among the various parts of the enemy to form an overarching system (or structure) that acts with a substantial degree of unity, like a physical body ... using the concept necessitates viewing the enemy holistically”.⁹³ Here we can clearly recognise a complex system approach that we mentioned previously. The CoG appears as a node holding a connected system together and that can be found only by looking at the whole. But Echevarria went further and added that “a center of gravity exerts a certain centripetal force that tends to hold an entire system or structure together; thus a blow at the center of gravity would throw an enemy off balance or even cause the entire system (or structure) to collapse”.⁹⁴

It is very interesting that there exists in complex system theory what is a very similar concept to the CoG: leverage points, also described as levers. The concept of leverage points was coined by system scientist Donella Meadows and corresponds to points where a “small shift in one thing can produce big changes in everything”.⁹⁵ This definition embeds non-linear thinking and is clearly related to Clausewitz “focal point of force and movement, upon which the larger whole depends”. Other scholars have noted the profound similarities between CoG and leverage points. Friedman wrote about the CoG that “there are concepts in complexity science and chaos theory that match Clausewitz’s description: levers or attractors”, which are “aspects of deterministic, nonlinear systems where inputs yield drastic and rapid change in the behavior of the system”. In the military, these levers would appear “as main efforts, as critical capabilities or critical vulnerabilities, or, more properly, as centers of gravity”. Note here the plural form, and while there maybe one main CoG, it is certainly more likely there

⁹² (Echevarria 2003)

⁹³ Ibid.

⁹⁴ Ibid.

⁹⁵ (Meadows 2008)

are a multitude of CoGs or levers. Theory has shown that single points of failure are unlikely by themselves to bring a complex system down.⁹⁶ Discussions on where the one and only CoG is located miss the point that there can be many CoGs, each with their specific characteristics changing as the conflict develops, as Clausewitz said a CoG can “advance or retreat”.⁹⁷

Therefore, and more generally, I argue that deep strategies first require creating a mental abstraction of one’s and adversary’s levers and to develop a system perspective of their co-dependencies and inter-reactions to stimuli. Following this proposition, if such model is translated into a strategic game akin to e.g. Diplomacy that can be played by AI, then we have a general framework that allows AI to solve strategic interactions.

Looking for levers

What is fundamental in modelling is that one should not aim to include everything. As explained in a previous section, models are simplified representations of the world, and as British statistician George Box said, “all models are wrong, some are useful”. This illustrates that even when bringing AI in strategy, strategy will remain both an art and a science because modelling is an art that uses and does science. The modeller chooses to retain the most important factors that he or she believes are important. The strategist similarly retains the most important factors, or levers, that he or she believes are important. Writing about war as a complex system, Cole does not say it differently: “the modeler decides what to focus on and what to avoid ... Modeling is an art form, and what is aggregated is dependent on what a modeler wishes to examine”. This is echoed by Brigadier General de Czege asserting that “trying to approach the problem from the perspective of a center of gravity leads you to see very quickly that some vulnerabilities are interesting but a waste of resources because they do not lead anywhere useful in the end”.⁹⁸

Importantly, there is nothing in Clausewitz that tells CoGs should be located at a specific level of war, either tactical, operational or strategic, and CoGs are instead better understood from a system perspective. In this regard, it is worth citing examples of CoGs given by

⁹⁶ (Cook 1998)

⁹⁷ (Clausewitz 2007)

⁹⁸ (de Czege 1988)

Clausewitz: “Alexander the Great, Gustavus Adolphus and Charles XII of Sweden, and Frederick the Great each had their centers of gravity in their respective armies. Had their armies been destroyed, these men would have been remembered as failures. In states with many factions vying for power, the center of gravity lies mainly in the capital; in small states supported by a more powerful one, it lies in the army of the stronger state; in alliances, it lies in the unity formed by common interests; in popular uprisings, it lies in the persons of the principal leaders and in public opinion”.⁹⁹ CoGs can therefore range from emperors, cities, armies, to leaders or public opinions. One could also add ideologies. Note that developing a mental model of these levers and their connectedness does not involve any use of computer.¹⁰⁰ It is indeed what strategists have done for centuries. However, computers become required when the complexity of the model and its internal dynamics exceed what the human mind can handle.

Wargames of levers

How would lever modelling relate to wargaming today?¹⁰¹ This question is not easily answered because wargames can take multiple forms and there is no simple agreed definition of what is a wargame. Wargames can be used for education and experiential learning, logistic analysis and planning for offensives and war. Lever modelling would come closer to the latter but some would not call this a wargame. A recent book on simulation and wargaming explains that “wargaming stands in contrast to but not in opposition to the computational analytical approach” as “the action of the wargame generates interactions and relationships that could not have been anticipated and relies upon the emergence of results not subject to prediction”.¹⁰² In my opinion, this is not correct and while the authors discuss wargames, they in practice describe a complex system model. Lever modelling would not only address one major critics of wargames being “a simulation of one replication” or a “sample size of one” but also allows to explore strategies in an entirely new way.¹⁰³ The advantage of adopting a model of war as a system of levers is that it becomes possible to have algorithms similar to

⁹⁹ (Clausewitz 2007)

¹⁰⁰ Although I have not seen instances where AI builds conceptual models of complex systems, it is no longer unreasonable to assume that an AI like ChatGPT may assist humans in listing levers in complex systems.

¹⁰¹ Another question could also ask how lever modelling relates to game theory. This is different. In a typical game, the prisoner’s dilemma, the two players can independently choose to remain silent or confess a crime. In a lever wargame, they would have the possibility to corrupt the policeman (his integrity being a lever) and be both freed.

¹⁰² (Turnitsa, Blais, and Tolk 2021)

¹⁰³ Ibid

DeepNash or Cicero and their future versions play the wargame. In particular, based on Cicero algorithm, one promising research avenue would be to train players based on their cultural references. For example, one possibility would be to modify Diplomacy to reflect the current geopolitical landscape of Europe or Eastern Asia and have an agent trained to behave like the Russian or Chinese president and test which strategies would lead to specific outcomes. The idea would be to create what are called “digital twins” of adversaries and to play against them in a game representing a specific geopolitical context. However, and while this may sound fascinating, it is also important to remind ourselves that there remain enormous challenges ahead, albeit and paradoxically, these challenges may lie more in the complex nature of war than in AI.

THE CHALLENGES FACED BY DEEP STRATEGIES

There are substantial challenges arising when aiming to develop models of strategies for further processing by AI. These challenges could already be anticipated when enumerating the predicaments of the strategist: strategy is an adversarial dialectic in a non-repeatable environment where cause-and-effect relationships are often unknown. Many of the challenges relate to the fact that “making and enacting strategy is an inherently psychological activity”.¹⁰⁴ Still, the psychological nature of strategy is often set aside, especially when quantitative or computational approaches are brought in. For example, in combat simulations “the human factors are either ignored or standardised and mirrored so as to make the basis of comparison as free from confounding factors as possible”.¹⁰⁵ A deep strategy approach should aim for the opposite because these confounding factors are likely to be the ones driving strategic outcomes. As Payne repeats “if we see strategy as instrumental or purposeful, political, social, and violent, one master theme unites these, whatever the local context: strategy is, at its core, a psychological phenomenon”.¹⁰⁶

Developing a theory of mind

A proper strategist, human or AI, must have an elaborated theory of mind which is the

¹⁰⁴ (Payne 2015)

¹⁰⁵ (Turnitsa, Blais, and Tolk 2021)

¹⁰⁶ (Payne 2018)

cognitive skill to represent other’s mental states and how they may have different thoughts, feelings, beliefs, and intentions.¹⁰⁷ This is known since the first strategy textbook: “know the enemy, know yourself, and victory is never in doubt”.¹⁰⁸ Zachary Shore advocates for what he calls strategic empathy, “the ability to think like [your] opponent”.¹⁰⁹ He explains that strategic empathy depends on identifying any divergence from a “continuity heuristics” of one’s adversary. Specifically, it is not in the pattern of previous behaviours but in a break in that pattern that one can understand what the intention of an adversary are.¹¹⁰ In a short article, Shore goes further and explains that “successful novelists are highly astute at developing strategic empathy for another’s character” and that the U.S. military would benefit from enlisting the help of people from the arts.¹¹¹ While these valid points may suggest that deep strategies will always fall short of human social skills, a more nuanced perspective is required, especially in light of recent advances in AI. A recent manuscript uploaded on the preprint server arXiv¹¹² suggests that large language models have now reached the ability to develop a theory of mind corresponding to a nine-year-old child.¹¹³ Shore argues that strategic empathy requires detecting breaks in patterns of behaviours, but pattern recognition is perhaps the task at which AI has been shown to excel. Similarly, Shore advocates for the military teaming up with novelists, but AI is now able to write novels that compare in quality with human-written novels.¹¹⁴ A properly trained AI may therefore very well excel in psychologically reading its adversaries.

Reading commitments and reputation

Still, it is unclear – for the moment – whether AI will be able to understand and master strategies where threats of the use of force play a role as important, if not more, than the use of force itself. Nobel prize Thomas Schelling explained that strategy is a form of dialogue involving signalling, commitments and reputations, and manipulations of risk.¹¹⁵ Schelling illustrated the importance of commitments with the ancient Xenophon stopping by an

¹⁰⁷ (Sabbagh and Bowman 2018)

¹⁰⁸ (Sun Tzu 2008)

¹⁰⁹ (Shore 2014)

¹¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹¹ (Shore 2012)

¹¹² In some disciplines, typically, mathematics and computer science, this pre-print server is the place where research teams post their manuscripts before publication.

¹¹³ (Kosinski 2023)

¹¹⁴ (Edwards 2023)

¹¹⁵ (Schelling 1980; 2008)

impassable cliff when hunted down by Persians: “one of his generals expressed alarm that they would have no escape. Xenophon reassured him: ‘As for the argument that ...we are putting a difficult ravine in our rear just when we are going to fight ... is not this really something that we ought to jump at? I should like the enemy to think it easy going in every direction for him to retreat. But we ought to learn from our very position that there is no safety for us except in victory’ ”.¹¹⁶ Here Schelling shows how cutting escape routes is a way to signal an adversary one’s commitment to victory. Would an AI have chosen the same battlefield? Commitments are at the core of deterrence (issuing threats to prevent an adversary from doing something) and compellence (issuing threats to force an adversary to do something or stop doing something – a term coined by Schelling himself). Deterrence is passive while compellence is active. In both cases however, there is a psychological game involved and AI does not seem to have reached the ability (yet) to master the commitment signals at the basis of that game, although this may be only a matter of time. This is nevertheless important, because as Schelling wrote about Berlin or Quemoy, outposts of the West in communist territory, the costs of defending them would perhaps exceed the benefits and a deep strategy might conclude that these places should not be worth defending. However, doing so would send a signal to adversaries that the U.S. is not serious about defending its allies or that perhaps not all allies need to be defended. Allies may then question whether they have made the right choice to ally themselves with the U.S. These questions have been at the core of strategic thinking during the Cold War, but there is no indication that an AI would master them.

Facing cognitive biases

In situations of extreme strategic tensions, deep strategies will also face the unexpected and apparently biased decisions made by humans. Specifically, it is well known that humans display cognitive biases, which have been found to handicap the proper processing of intelligence.¹¹⁷ However, it has also been argued that cognitive biases may, on the contrary, be adaptive and bring strategic benefits.¹¹⁸ Cognitive biases are mental heuristics that have been shaped by evolution to help us solve strategic interactions that have reoccurred in our past. Despite the incomparable complexity of the modern world, many strategic interactions

¹¹⁶ (Schelling 2007)

¹¹⁷ (Heuer 1999)

¹¹⁸ (Johnson 2020)

between country or army leaders remain remarkably similar to the strategic interactions between leaders of early human groups. Thucydides for example argued that “fear, honour, and interest” were the fundamental human motivations that drove states to war, regardless of their rationalisations or justifications.¹¹⁹ Cognitive biases, such as overconfidence or attribution error, may be strategic adaptations to these psychological invariants of human social life. In that context, a perfectly rational deep strategist may do worse than a human. First, being rational makes one entirely predictable, second, a rational strategy may perform poorly against an irrational one, and third, and conversely, being irrational can bring advantages against a rational actor. Johnson stresses that “effective strategies often differ radically from those predicted by conventional paradigms, such as rational choice theory”.¹²⁰ Even one of the known advantages of AI against humans – an immense capacity to store information and to immediately access it – may not perform as well as the memory distortion exhibited by humans, because the latter allows to generate new scenarios. Since the future is not always like the past, one can intuitively understand how “remembering” events that have not occurred may be adaptive when handling future novel events. Therefore, what political scientists, economists and intelligence analysts view as “decision-making problems” may be for strategists “elegant solutions to decision-making problems.” Kenrick and Griskevicius explain that “being accurate is not always smart”.¹²¹ If deep strategies are always accurate, does it mean then they will sometimes not be smart? It is however too early to tell how AI will treat cognitive biases when doing strategy and whether it will be entirely rational or exhibit some cognitive biases and if the latter, whether these biases will be human-inspired or machine-inspired in a way we cannot foresee. Still a preview may have been given during game 4 of the match between Lee Sedol and AlphaGo in 2016, where Lee Sedol decided to play an aggressive and risky strategy to disturb AlphaGo’s apparent prudent strategy. It worked and the AI ended up making erratic moves before giving up.

Escaping the maelstrom of system effects

A different set of challenges relates to the complex nature of war. As Friedman argues, when adopting a complex system approach “the key concept is that not just the variables are time-dependent, but the parameters and relationships among the variables can evolve over time”.

¹¹⁹ (Thucydides 1972)

¹²⁰ (Johnson 2020)

¹²¹ (Kenrick and Griskevicius 2013)

Said otherwise, it is particularly difficult, perhaps impossible, to foresee how adversaries will react after a sequence of adversarial actions between adversaries has taken place. Thinking in systems requires to think in terms of knock-on effects, indirect results or nth-order consequences which are likely to be more important than the first expected consequence that justified the chosen action. Examples abound in wars and international relations. John Gaddis explained that creating institutional arrangements after WWI with the goal to preserve peace did not prevent a second world war, while the institutions post-WWII without no such design were marked by a long peace.¹²² Similarly, after biological warfare was banned in 1925 by the Geneva Protocol, the Japanese concluded that this must be a promising way of warfare to pursue since it would otherwise not have been banned.¹²³ Jervis explained that “many of the successes of Henry Kissinger ... were the unintended consequences of his failure to understand how others would react”.¹²⁴ Because a strategic action intends to close paths to adversaries, they will react by overcoming closures or exploring new unanticipated paths. When choosing among options, strategists need to be particularly careful to the role of interactions between factors. One action may be ineffective but only because it requires a second concomitant action. Interactions may not be linear and require one or both actions to reach a critical threshold before generating strategic effect. The order of actions may also be important: considering human aversion to losses, a loss of 20% of a country followed by a reconquest of half of that loss may be more conducive to peace negotiations than a direct loss of 10%. The same can be said regarding the sequential order of threats and concessions. Some actions may not have consequences until a long time has passed because adversaries need time to adapt. While such actions may look ineffective, they may on the contrary be more effective than actions against which adversaries react immediately. System effects are also obviously shaped by the adversarial nature of strategy. Believing an adversary will not take an action makes it more likely because the adversary knows nobody expects it will take that action: “in war it is precisely the things which are thought impossible which most often succeed, when they are well conducted”.¹²⁵ Conversely, expecting an adversary to take an action and preparing accordingly makes this action less likely because the adversary knows counter-preparations are being made. This is why strategic paranoia can retrospectively be found unjustified but only because it had strategic effects. Actions also change the

¹²² (Gaddis 1989)

¹²³ (Harris and Paxman 2002)

¹²⁴ (Jervis 1997)

¹²⁵ (Browning 1995)

environment where they take place and while this means that repeating a similar action may produce different outcomes, it also means that smart strategists can take action but only to modify their environment to leverage the effects of subsequent actions. However, understanding the ripple effects that any action will cause in a system is generally beyond human abilities and it may also be beyond AI abilities. The reason is not that algorithms are not advanced enough yet or because compute power is still limited. The reason is that no algorithm or computer can reliably know something that cannot be known simply because it has not happened yet.

The long march of deep strategies

These challenges, and many others that will emerge as AI develops, will determine whether and how AI can be used in real world strategic interactions. We can anticipate more impressive breakthroughs in deep strategies, as shown with the ability of AI to find optimal strategies for strategic games, even now in games where it is required to demonstrate negotiation, persuasion or betrayal skills. Difficulties will however persist regarding understanding what adversaries commit to and signal – would an AI understand the ambiguous signals of an adversary leaning towards de-escalation while preserving its reputation? Difficulties will also remain when an adversary strategy is to create non-linearity in a system dynamic because “one’s opponent is not always playing by the same rules, and is often, in the effort to win, attempting to change what rules there are”.¹²⁶ A striking example of such discontinuity in war are the Japanese kamikazes during the Pacific War after 1944. Nimitz said that “kamikazes took the Navy by surprise since designed suicide had not been a part of American air doctrine”.¹²⁷ When the rules of the game are changed by an adversary, it is unclear what advantages an AI will have against human strategists.

CONCLUSION

We can already foresee from the challenges above that AI is unlikely to make the predicaments of the strategist belong to history any time soon. Still, does it mean that deep

¹²⁶ (Beyerchen 1992)

¹²⁷ (Millett and Maslowski 2012)

strategic theory is also unlikely to develop? I believe the answer to this question needs to be nuanced, there will be domain of conflicts, where deep strategies will provide better understanding. These domains are perhaps those where the possibility of changing rules is limited, at the tactical level, assuming no new game-changing weapon is introduced, or at the geoeconomic level.

Strategic grammar studies

We can however envision that deep strategies may be useful to propose some sort of general strategic grammar. It is interesting to compare with networks, which can take different forms, like the internet or food webs in ecosystems, etc, but for which a unifying theory exists.¹²⁸ Strategy lacks a similar unifying theory. Adopting a complex system approach to adversarial interactions may open avenues to sketch out this theory. It would describe strategic interactions at a very abstract level, where adversaries would be modelled by their levers and their interconnectedness. It would propose metrics to describe strategic interactions and set general principles. These principles would need to be such as to remain valid without attempting to predict outcomes of strategic interactions, which we have seen, is not possible due to the complex nature of war. They would make abstraction of idiosyncrasies, while retaining the strategic relevance of idiosyncrasies and could generalise across strategic situations. Deep strategic theory would allow for crisis or war replay. With e.g. Meta AI's Cicero-like agents trained based on the writings, speeches and behaviours of Hitler or Stalin and put in wargames replicating the geopolitical context of the time, it would be interesting to find out how an AI would play to avoid war. In a more academic enquiry style, such Cicero-like approach could better explore the psychological conditions under which e.g. the security dilemma emerges. Deep strategy theory would also test whether strategic precepts such as Sun Tzu's are always valid. By using simple models of strategic interactions, with agents trained to follow or ignore Sun Tzu's precepts to various degrees, one could find which of these precepts drive strategies. A whole field of scholarship is opening, which would honour Clausewitz's description of his theory as being "capable of growth".¹²⁹ Deep strategies may turn out to be a way to understand Clausewitz better. A new paradox of strategy may however emerge and reveal that strategic success is often driven by chance since knowledge of what is

¹²⁸ (Barabási and Pósfai 2016)

¹²⁹ (Clausewitz 2007)

happening is uncertain and knowledge of what has not yet happened is impossible.¹³⁰

When applied to real world strategic interactions, deep strategies could possibly find innovative strategic combinations that humans had not thought of, as happened in Move 37, or by playing with many coups in advances that humans cannot compute, as AI does in Go. Deep strategies may be different from usual human strategies as AI will not be driven by emotions. An important parameter determining the nature of deep strategies will be the utility or pay-off functions that algorithms are told to maximize. Without factoring in human casualties, deep strategies may exceed what is politically tolerable. With it, we may find strategies more in the line of Liddell Hart's indirect approach. In many cases, the nature of which utility to maximise will be difficult to set as real-world goals of war may be blurry. Naturally, these deep strategies will be entirely dependent on the appropriateness of interconnections and feedback loops between different levers across levels of war, such as political, economic, social, cultural or technological. But again, this has nothing to do with AI per se and falls under the exact same challenges that strategists have faced across centuries. What a formal lever model does is only to narrow down the domain of hidden subjectivity that is the realm of the strategist brain by making explicit the assumptions in strategic interactions. The only thing that AI adds is to find strategic combinations that are innovative and involve a depth impossible by humans to compute.

Strategists shape strategies

Because AI can guarantee a Nash optimality to strategies, it will be difficult for humans to compete against deep strategies when models are realistic and capture well the nature of the strategic interaction. However, it does not immediately follow that humans will never be able to outsmart deep strategies. Recall that deep strategies are not free from human inputs, and therefore biases and cognitive limits, since models of levers are made by humans or by AI trained from human data. Deep strategy may therefore exert a selection pressure that will retain only the best and brightest human strategists, those able to imagine and create unexpected events that nobody envisioned and that redraw the rules of the game. Some have already envisioned this dynamic: "when cheaper prediction is applied in a political context that is as challenging and uncertain as warfare, then quality data and sound judgment become

¹³⁰ Strictly speaking, since there is no data about the future, there cannot be any knowledge about it.

extremely valuable. Adversaries, in turn, will take steps to undermine the quality of data and judgment by manipulating information and violating expectations. Correcting for adversarial countermeasures will further increase the complexity of judgment, which exacerbates the inherent friction and frustration of war”.¹³¹ Deep strategies will drive strategic interactions towards the creation of non-linearities, which can be anticipated only by humans. In a competition between human and AI, it will probably make strategic genius even more important, giving right to Clausewitz. Said otherwise, average strategists will be defeated by deep strategies, but it will be still be possible to defeat deep strategies by practicing the purest form of strategy: breaking rules. One possible outcome may be the emergence of computer assisted or computer augmented strategies where human and AI work together to develop strategies. Indeed, Go players have improved their playing styles by learning from AlphaGo.¹³² However, a new psychological dimension of strategy will appear: what will humans choose to do when deep strategies conflict with their psychological instincts, especially given Clausewitz’s claim that “action can never be based on anything firmer than instinct”?

What is however certain is that deep strategies will exacerbate the power of multinational corporations such as Google, Meta or Microsoft. Multinational corporations have enormous research budgets, massive training data and gigantic computer power. It is informative to quote a report by NATO: “DeepMind’s AlphaStar approach cannot simply be copied. On the one hand, it turned out that the methods used were not all completely disclosed after all, on the other hand, the resources available in the study do not even come close to the computing capacity that DeepMind had available for AlphaStar”.¹³³ One could suggest that crowd-sourcing computational efforts may help but attempts have not been conclusive: “a distributed, open-source effort to reproduce DeepMind’s results, called Leela Chess Zero, has taken approximately 1 year to reach the strength of Stockfish, using essentially the same approach as AlphaZero”.¹³⁴ The growing influence of the industry has been singled out as an important problem¹³⁵ and we can probably start talking about ‘compute inequality’ where the computer power in the world is restricted to a handful of corporations. This brings profound policy and strategic implications. States will struggle because while they can benefit from

¹³¹ (Goldfarb and Lindsay 2022)

¹³² (Shin et al. 2023)

¹³³ (Doll et al. 2021)

¹³⁴ (Moy and Shekh 2019). Stockfish is an open-source chess AI developed in the early 2000s.

¹³⁵ (Ahmed, Wahed, and Thompson 2023)

their own corporations, they will never know whether these corporations use AI to manipulate them. When the interests of e.g. DeepMind and the U.S. are antagonist, how could the State Department be sure that DeepMind is not running a deep strategy to systematically win against the U.S.?¹³⁶

Final words

I conclude by recommending that it is wise to not disregard present and future advances in AI. For example, AI is already shaping the conflict in Ukraine through a rather discrete but influential company, Palantir, which provides a suite of algorithms to identify complex patterns in huge datasets.¹³⁷ Referring back to Freedman writing that “AI will never be a true strategist”, I believe this is too categorical. Instead, humans will no longer be the only strategist on the battlefield but that does not mean AI will not face the same predicaments. As such, AI will not always beat human strategists, but human strategists with AI will likely beat human strategists without AI.

¹³⁶ Elon Musk’s “peace plan” for Ukraine suggestions are an illustration this hypothesis may not be too far-fetched.

¹³⁷ (Ignatius 2022)

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